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Development of Web-Based Price Comparison System for Orgone Accumulator Based Farm Products and Other Local Farm Commodities.

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Abstract

The business-to-consumer aspect of electronic commerce (e-commerce) is the most visible business use of the internet today. The primary purpose of e-commerce websites is to sell goods online. However, all e-commerce websites operating in Nigeria do not provide the customer a way of comparing prices of products before going to the market for shopping or making order and also our local products are not captures on most of the existing e-commerce website. This paper therefore seeks to bridge the gap by developing a web application to allow customers to compare products prices before going to the market for shopping or making order taking into consideration only our local products. It provides the user with a catalog of different products from different markets in different shops available for purchase together with their different prices. In order to develop a web application like this, there is need to study and understand a number of Technologies. These include multi-tiered architecture, client and server scripting languages, implementation technologies such as contents management system (C.M.S), relational database such as MySQL. After studying these technologies, the web application is implemented using a 3-tier approach, with a MySQL backend database, CSS for layout design and HTML/PHP incorporated in Dreamweaver as the front end client. Test and evaluation results showed that the system perform satisfactorily with the commodities from the orgone accumulator having the best price and quality.

Key words: Orgone Accumulator, Farm products, Dreamweaver, prices comparison and e-commerce.

A. Introduction

Agriculture and commerce has been one of the major ways of human survival right from the beginning of human history. Commerce can be defined as business activities and components, as well as functions and institutions involved in transferring goods from the producer to the consumer [1]. Technological innovations have over the years transformed commercial activities globally. This can be seen in the way innovative technologies quickened the pace of the industrial revolution and gave rise to mass production and our global economic system.

A technological innovation that transformed commerce was telecommunication. There was a time when the telegraph ruled the business world. According to the, the telegraph led to the fax machine, which in turn made rapid information transfer in the business world possible. The telegraph transfers information in a similar way twitter does, that is, short and direct. The invention of Television also played a very important role in the world of business [8]. One of the recent technological innovations that is revolutionizing commerce today is the internet. The Internet has and continues to change the course of human history and is doing so at far greater speed than the other great disruptive technologies of the 20th century, such as electricity and the telephone. According to the economist magazine (1999) Ask any signed-up member of the “digirati” (The elite of the computer industry and online communities) and you will be told that the Internet is the most transforming invention in human history. It has the capacity to change everything, the way we work, the way we learn and play, and perhaps, even the way we sleep. [5]. What is more, it is doing so at far greater speed than the other great disruptive technologies of the 20th century, such as electricity, the telephone and the automobile. [13].

With internet, physical boundaries are removed enabling one to carry out business transactions anywhere via computing devices, at any time. Commercial transactions can take place anywhere which enhances customer

January 31, 2019

convenience. In most developed and developing nations of the world, E-commerce activities contribute a significant percentage to the gross domestic product (GDP) of these nations [13]. These developments have largely been enhanced by massive ICT developments in these nations, and Nigeria is speedily catching up with the rest of the world in this regard. In Nigeria, e-commerce activities were first noticed in the year 2009 with the emergence of some websites including Tafoo.com, jumia.com.ng, and konga.com [23]. Tafoo.com is one of the pioneer E-commerce website based in Lagos. It's a home for wearable items. Tafoo.com was followed by now two of the most popular E-commerce website in Nigeria. [3]Jumia.com.ng and konga.com both founded in the year 2012. People can find virtually their entire house hold supplies on jumia and konga, ranging from consumer electronics to fashion products, and would definitely other items of interest when shopping on one of the two. Beside the previous websites, there exists another website, kaymu.com also founded the same 2012. Kaymu.com offers different services and their business model basically revolves around creating online market platforms that allow buyers and sellers carryout transactions on their website. [13].

With the aforementioned impact of E-commerce technology in Nigeria, there is need for further simplification in order to bring the benefit of e-commerce to the Nigerian common man. As a result, this paper proposes to create a platform that will integrate our local market places with online markets by providing an avenue that allows local marketers to showcase their commodities and give us room to compare the orgone accumulator product with other local farm products, and for buyers to see and get prior knowledge of where to get the best in terms of price and quality.

B. Aim and Objectives

The aim of this project to create an environment or platform where people can easily get instant prices of various local commodities at different location in their nearby local market as compare to orgone accumulator charge. This will give the buyer the ability to choose where to get the best quality and price, thereby creating competition among the businessmen. In order to achieve this aim, we have identified the following core objectives which have been designated as fundamental to the project:

1. To develop a back-end database to store details of different shops and business in a nearby market.
2. To identify sample goods and collect the data that will be used to populate the database
3. To develop a web-based front end on which visitors can access the prices of different commodities for comparison.
4. To create a platform for the customer to place order of the commodities of their choice
5. To create access control in order to ensure that only authorized people are able to upload or update information on the database

C. Orgone accumulator

Dr. Heckman investigated the response of plants to orgone exposure and explored the potential application of orgone energy to agronomic and horticultural crop production. In 1976, he exposed tomato seeds to orgone energy and found that the irradiated seeds produced a greater number of fruits and flowers than did the control group of seeds. Heckman went on to conduct further experiments in 1981, 1983, 1985, and 1986. In 1981, the exposed seeds produced fewer but larger potatoes. In 1983, using a five-fold accumulator, he achieved a 50% increase in yield from seeds exposed to orgone energy for one hour. However, to his surprise, he discovered that seeds irradiated for 10 hours produced only a 23% increase in yield [17].

In a number of early experiments, the vines of the plants seemed to be strongly affected by seed exposure to orgone energy. They lived longer on average, and some never died. In 1986, orgone irradiation led to a reduced yield from treated seeds [2].

Although he achieved mixed results in his studies, Dr. Heckman maintained that the orgone accumulator may have a number of promising applications in agriculture:

- charging seeds before planting
- treating seedlings prior to transplanting
- irradiating cuttings for reproduction
- healing graft wounds
- charging irrigation water
- charging potting soil
- increasing the longevity of stored seeds
- post harvest seed storage

He noted that while environmental conditions were crucial for plant growth, more research into the use of Orgone accumulators in agriculture could lead to valuable results.

D. Literature Reviews

The marketplace and the way the business is conducted will never be the same. E-commerce applications began in the early 1970s with such innovations as electronic transfer of funds [11]. However, the applications were limited to large corporations and a few daring small businesses. Then came electronic data interchange (EDI), which added other kinds of transaction Processing and extended participation to all industries [17]. Since the commercialization of the Internet and the introduction of the Web in the early 1990s, E-Commerce applications have rapidly expanded. Kreyon Systems [28] this system offers an in-depth experience in business process automation for various sectors. However, the system is only limited mainly on Business automation.

Cash Craft Asset Management 3rd Floor Asei World Centre 57 Aba Road, Port-Harcourt, Rivers, Nigeria, Light House Asset Management Ltd 3rd Floor, Oyo State House Ralph Sodeinde Street, Central Business District, Abuja, Asset Management Corporation Of Nigeria (AMCON) 3rd Floor, Murjanatu House, 1, Zambezi Crescent, Maitama, Abuja, ARM Asset Management 1 Mekunwen Road, Off Oyinkan Abayomi Drive, Ikoyi, Lagos, Nigeria, Tower Asset Management Limited Suite 6, 2nd Floor, Marina Court, Plot 252A Herbert Macaulay Way, CBD, Abuja FCT and Cowry Asset Management Ltd. Plot 1319 Karimu Kotun, Victoria Island, Lagos Nigeria, Cash Craft Asset Management services, includes stock brokering and asset management services in Nigeria all the above systems focuses mainly on stock and asset management.. [29][30][31][32][33][34]

According to [4], they explore the possibility of creating a product search engine that is able to dynamically find commercial sites, independent of merchant feeds and other human involvement in the management of internal databases. They evaluate briefly the constraints of current shopping search engines and the benefits of offering a fully automated version. In addition, the application of JTidy, Stemmers and Wrappers, in order to extract the relevant information from a commercial website. Their result showed sufficient evidence that there is some level of convention and structure among commercial sites for wrapper functions to extract information reasonably. However, they were surprised to find that the functions that we have developed have achieved a substantial amount of success. they also restricted themselves to a small set of web sites. They recommend that the diversity of the wider web and the constant change that it undergoes only means that further investigation is necessary to determine the viability of a fully automated product search engine. The content of these websites may simply become more diversified and irregular to warrant the applicability of any set of heuristics in the long-term. Nonetheless, as the web develops, there may be greater standardization among online stores. In the Internet market, websites are the main interface between online merchants and their customers. Effective website design plays a critical role in attracting and maintaining customers. Interest and in influencing their purchase behavior. Despite the singular significance of website design, little theoretical knowledge is available regarding how web-design elements impact the purchase behavior of online shoppers. By drawing on the theory

January 31, 2019

of planned behavior and interpersonal influence, we develop and empirically test a conceptual model for the process by which web design elements could influence the purchase intention of online customers. This research provides a theoretical framework for the design decisions regarding websites in order to accommodate the salient features of online shopping. [6].

Companies implement different frameworks and best practices with the objective to improve the project Management success rate and improve the business adaptability to the changing business environment. Project Management framework (PRINCE2) and agile development framework (Scrum) proved in many cases that they can meet. [10]. However, both frameworks are based on different principles and the use of both frameworks together were carefully considered. A large amount of money and effort has been invested by companies into establishing their project management environment and processes that follow the classical phased approach where requirements were defined upfront and fixed. But companies want to react more quickly to new global challenges and to the changing business environment. These business requirements then result in the failure of many running projects. Therefore, there is a need to enhance the current project management environment so that it is more agile and adoptive to changes. In their work, they create a conceptual framework that aggregates principles and processes from both frameworks (PRINCE2 and Scrum) with emphasis on their use in web development projects. This paper will discuss the advantages and disadvantages of using the two abovementioned frameworks. [19].

In his work, design and implementation of a small web shop for online business for customers who can shop at home by a computer and the seller sell the product products and services without the huge amount of maintenance cost for the management and marketing in the real storefront. He concluded that the task is simply to establish a Web shop system by analyzing, web user interface designing, database constructing and connecting, testing and implementing. It uses ASP (Active Server Pages), HTML (Hyper Text Markup Language), VBScript, JavaScript for implementing and bases on Microsoft Access for handing the database. The system is divided into front-stage and back-stage management page. Front-stage management is friendly interface for users to browse, inquire. It includes: browse products, check products, order items, view shopping cart, user maintenance and other functions. Back-stage management is available to administrators, it includes: product management, user management, order management and so on. The administrators from the tedious manual operation freed and increase office efficiency. Additionally, the whole research and developing work are based on course materials. some existing systems (such as ebay) were compared. After that, the proposed system was analyzed and modified by following and resolving some real problems and needs from some online shops. [20]

In their work, A Conceptual Framework for E-Commerce (EC) Innovation in Chinese SME they argued that EC development can only be valuable when it is treated as a dynamic innovation process rather than implementation of western models. This conceptual framework, however, is mostly based on literature review and only qualitatively supported by the e-SMEs in Hangzhou Area. As E-Commerce is rapidly gaining popularity in China, EC innovation becomes a major growth strategy for many SMEs. Meanwhile, problems and challenges are hindering proliferation of EC innovation. The need exists for a theoretical model to forge EC innovation: a dynamic process with progressive stages of both internal and external e-readiness. Derived from theories and evidenced by the case studies from Hangzhou, China, it reveals to them that top management, organizational learning, government support, market forces, and technology readiness as essential in each development stage, but with different emphasis on integrating strategic management, innovation management, and entrepreneurship development perspectives.

EC development can only be valuable when it is treated as a dynamic innovation process rather than implementation of western models. According to them China is undergoing a strategic transition from its long-

time sole focus on traditional manufacturing businesses to a more service-oriented digital economy. [2]. The EC volume is only a small part of the entire domestic commerce and one third of the EC volume in the United States. Forging and facilitating EC model innovations is the only way out for e-SMEs to change the game and generate significant new value for customers and the firms [19].

E. Materials and Methods

System development methodology is a method or process to develop and build a system with a series of steps or operations that can be defined as a system life cycle model. Alternatively, a methodology can be described as a collection of procedures, techniques, tools and documentation aids, which helps system developers to implement a new information system, which consists of a set of phases, followed by a set of sub phases. [12] In theory, there are four general phases for real world system development as shown in Figure 1 that includes system requirements (needs, resource) as input and a finished or completed product as output. Requirements are determined, and then the analysis is performed. After the analysis is completed, a design of the system is produced, followed by the implementation of the complete software/system product.

Figure 1: System Development Process Model in Theory

The Waterfall model is our chosen software development methodology for this project. The waterfall model derives its name from the cascading effect from one phase to the other as is illustrated in figure 2 below.

Fig 2: The Waterfall model

The waterfall model is a suitable model because, in this model each phase has a well-defined starting and ending point, with identifiable deliveries to the next phase, Testing is inherent to every phase of the waterfall model and it is an enforced disciplined approach. It is documentation driven, that is, documentation is produced at every stage. Waterfall model is used as a model of Price Comparison systems. The waterfall model consists of stages that are cascading from one to another. One development stage should be completed before the next begins. The Waterfall model presents a very high level view of activities taking place during development, and it suggests to developers the sequence of events they should expect to encounter. Systems design is the process of defining the architecture, components, modules, interfaces, and data for a system to satisfy specified requirements. Systems design could be seen as the application of systems theory to product development.

The program was developed using PHP. PHP, which is short for Hypertext Preprocessor, is a server side programming language for creating dynamic web applications. Usability, adaptability, flexibility and scalability are desirable features which a web application should possess. PHP’s capacity to enable the development and deployment of web applications with these features has made its use in the web industry widespread.

Platform independence is another feature of PHP which made it suitable for developing this application. PHP is compatible with all famous operating systems such as Linux, Unix, Windows, Solaris. It is also compatible with servers such as Apache and IIS. Cross platform compatibility is one other advantage PHP. [15]

Forms and controls were created in HTML and PHP scripts were written to direct them to perform required actions. The database was created in MySQL and linked to the PHP environment.

Our system is of a three-tiered architecture. It is divided into three parts as shown in the system architecture diagram below:

Figure 3 depicts our system architecture.

F. Result and Discussions

In developing our system, the application platform used was Dreamweaver, Dreamweaver is a widely used enterprise computing platform developed under PHP Community Process. The platform provides an API and runtime environment for developing and running enterprise software, including network and web services, and other large-scale, multi-tiered, scalable, reliable, and secure network applications, providing an API for object-relational mapping, distributed and multi-tier architectures, and web services.

January 31, 2019

The platform incorporates a design based largely on modular components running on an application server. Dreamweaver is primarily developed in the PHP programming language. The platform emphasizes convention over configuration and annotations for configuration. Optionally XML can be used to override annotations or to deviate from the platform defaults.

Our system is architecturally divided into two parts: the client side; and the server side. The client is built with HTML, CSS and Dreamweaver, for building user interfaces that runs on the browser. The server side, on the other hand was implemented using the Dreamweaver APIs. Moreover, the final app is deployed on glassfish server, a Dreamweaver compliant application server that runs on Linux, Windows and Mac OS.

Database Requirements (Specification and Plan)

The database for the system can be built on a number of database models. A database model is a type of model that determines the logical structure of a database and fundamentally determines in which manner data can be stored, organized and manipulated. There are basically four types of model: hierarchical, network, relational and object model. The most popular is the relational model which was introduced by E.F Codd in 1970.

A relational database model is one whose symbols are organized into a collection of relations. Relational model has a number of advantages over the other models such as ease of use, flexibility, precision, reduced data redundancy, reduced inconsistencies in records, data independence, easy addition and removal of data and increased security of data. Therefore, the relational database model was used for building the database and MYSQL is the relational database model of choice. The database schema described in table 1 below:

Table 1. database schema

S/NO	FELD NAME	DATA TYPE	FIELD SIZE
1	product_id	AUTONUMBER	AUTONUMBER
2	Description	VARCHAR	40
3	Shop_owner	VARCHAR	60
4	Address	VARCHAR	70
5	Picdesc	VARCHAR	200
6	Price	DECIMAL	10,2

Functional Requirements

A functional requirement describes an interaction between the system and its environment. The functional requirements are detailed below in terms of the modules and sections available in the prototype that interact with the environment. Below are the functional requirements of the price comparison system.

1. Admin Login

This feature allows the central admin of the system to use his credentials to login to the system. The central admin credentials are preloaded in the database during the implementation stage

The following menu items are displayed once the admin is successfully logged in:

The image shows a screenshot of an 'E-Commerce System' login page. At the top, there is a green header bar with the text 'E-Commerce System'. Below this is a pink-bordered box titled 'Authentication Details'. Inside this box, there are two input fields: 'User Name' and 'Password', each with a corresponding text box. Below these fields is a green 'Login' button.

Plate 4.1: snapshot of Admin Login

- 1) **Manage Products:** This provides an interface for adding, updating and deleting
- 2) products and their types
- 3) **List of Shops:** Manages profile of registered shops by adding, updating or deleting shop information on the system.

Plate 4.1.2: Snapshot of Admin menu

2. Shop Owner Login

The shop owner is the actor on the system that also logs in using his username and password. This is initially generated when the shop owner is registered by the central admin. After successful login, a home page is presented along with a menu specific to the user. These include: manage Prices Menu item for managing the prices of products in the shop.

The image shows a screenshot of an 'E-Commerce System' login page, identical to the one in Plate 4.1. It features a green header bar with 'E-Commerce System', a pink-bordered box titled 'Authentication Details', and two input fields for 'User Name' and 'Password', followed by a green 'Login' button.

Plate 4.2: Snapshot of Shop owner's login

3. Products Page

January 31, 2019

Browse products is a feature on the price comparison website that allow customers to view prices of different products from different shops. This feature provides the following menu items

- 1) View Products: Allow customers to view list of different products from different shops together with their prices.

Plate 4.3.1: Snapshot of View Products

4. Manage Shops

This feature allows the admin to manage shops on the system. The menu items here include:

- 1) Manage Shop: The admin uses this menu item to add, update and delete shop records

5. View Prices

This feature is accessible to customers from the website. Customers can go to the website and browse the list of products together with their various prices.

Plate 4.5: Snapshot of Products

4.3 Testing

The objective of this testing phase is to prove that our system satisfies the requirements defined earlier. Several types of tests are conducted in this phase. This is an important phase of system development because it can ensure the system matches the specifications. Besides that, testing also ensures that the system functions in the correct and proper manner with the minimum amount of errors. Websites are susceptible to bugs and malfunctions, such as broken links, links that go to the wrong page, video and audio that not play properly, and scripts that not run properly. Besides that, there might be browser compatibility problems because a project may run perfectly on one browser but may not display properly on another browser.

Below are snapshot of a tomatoes comparison, order placement and order update by a customer

January 31, 2019

LOCAL COMMODITIES eCOMMERCE PORTAL					
LIST OF SHOPS THAT SELLS TOMATO					
S/No	Picture	Shop Owner	Address	Price	Price Diff(Price - Lowest Price)
1		Lagbaja	Natako	210.00	28
2		John Oyegun	Phase 8	200.00	18
3		Ocheni Uhiene	New Market, Shop 56	195.00	13
4		Bello Yahaya	New Market, Shop 76	182.00	0
Highest Price:210.00 From Lagbaja At Natako					
Lowest Price:182.00 From Bello Yahaya At New Market, Shop 76					
Home					

Plate 4.6: Snapshot of Compared Products Prices

Order Processing			
Order Details		Customer Details	
Shop Owner	<input type="text" value="Lagbaja"/>	Name	<input type="text" value="Engr. Saleh"/>
Address	<input type="text" value="Natako"/>	Address	<input type="text" value="Anyigba"/>
Price	<input type="text" value="210.00"/>	mobile No.	<input type="text" value="08063895729"/>
Product	<input type="text" value="TOMATO"/>		
Quantity	<input type="text" value="2"/>		
Amount	<input type="text" value="420"/>		
<input type="button" value="Home"/>		<input type="button" value="Order"/>	

Plate 4.7: Snapshot of the Order Placement

LOCAL COMMODITIES eCOMMERCE PORTAL										
CURRENT ORDERS for 121782356										
S/No	Name	Order ID	Address	Mobile No	Product	Quantity	Price	Amount	Order Date	Order Status
1	Adelaye Mayowa	10	House 45 500 unit Lokoja	906783345	POTATO	280	56	15680	0000-00-00	New

LOCAL COMMODITIES eCOMMERCE PORTAL										
CURRENT ORDERS for 121782356										
S/No	Name	Order ID	Address	Mobile No	Product	Quantity	Price	Amount	Order Date	Order Status
1	Engr. Saleh	5c03cadeaabf8	Anyigba	2147483647	TOMATO	210	2	420	0000-00-00	New

Plate 4.8: Snapshot of the Order Placement Update

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January 31, 2019

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January 31, 2019

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